

D 5.3a Numeric 3D-models of main streets in their present situation

Analysis of historical linear settlements and their development applying the UPMsmart methodology

by Angelika Psenner, Daniel Loeschenbrand and Susanne Tobisch, TU Wien

emc2 - WP5

Intro

Intro

Results

Phase 1

1.1 Approach

Historical linear settlements characterise Vienna's present-day urban periphery. These village structures under discussion, which cultivated the hinterland outside the consolidated city of Vienna, and the connecting streets between the villages formed focal points for urbanisation processes in the 19th and 20th centuries. The architectural orientation of the buildings and the planned village layout along the central main street, have the potential to make these settlements an integral part of an EMC2 'main street mesh'. With their linear core (the main street) and the connecting paths between villages, these settlements already formed an original historical 'main street mesh'. In contemporary contexts, these linear settlements frequently constitute components of primary street networks, thereby incorporating characteristics and qualities associated with village life and small-scale spatial configurations. The characteristics of these settlements – some of which are attributed to sociological factors (points of identification within cityscape) – in conjunction with their geographical distribution, characterised by villages situated at regular intervals of ca. 30 minutes on foot, renders them highly relevant to the concept of a 15-minute city on the outskirts.

One of the key objectives of this study is to use CAD-based three-dimensional models to draw conclusions regarding the functionality and spatial qualities of these village structures. The internationally acknowledged method 'UPM' (Urban Parterre Modeling) developed by Angelika Psenner is employed here; for the purposes of this analysis, it has been methodologically modified into 'UPMsmart'. The UPM method is utilised to create three-dimensional models of the street space and directly adjacent buildings, thus capturing their historical and present-day states. The primary focus is the ground floor zone, encompassing the utilisation of the space.

This model and methodology description (Deliverable 5.3) opens with an elaboration of the methodological background and the subsequent development of UPMsmart. The ensuing section will provide a detailed exposition of the UPMsmart methodology, underpinned by a systematic modelling protocol and followed by a comprehensive description of the model's constituent elements. In conclusion, the CAD-based models of the four linear settlement structures are presented and selected parameters from the model are evaluated in order to draw corresponding conclusions regarding the functioning of the linear settlements, their spatial qualities, and the significance of such three-dimensional models.

1.2 Explanation of UPM

Urban Parterre Modelling (UPM) facilitates a highly detailed qualitative analysis of the interaction between buildings, ground floor zones and street spaces. The development of UPM was initiated as part of a multi-year research project. The primary focus of UPM is to investigate the urban micro-structure (building level). The UPM method encompasses the historical and current state of each building along the respective research streets. This is achieved through a combination of archival research and on-site investigations. The usage of the buildings at unit level is meticulously documented, with this information being available in the building archives in Vienna (MA 37). The core phase of the methodology under discussion involves the utilisation of computer-aided design (CAD) software for the modelling of the edifices. This facilitates the formulation of highly detailed statements regarding the relationships and functions of ground floor zones and public spaces on a morphological level. UPM is characterised by its meticulous precision and attention to detail, including the modelling of individual buildings and their usages according to archive plans.

While this method produces meaningful and detailed results, the approach is inherently time-consuming and labour-intensive, which significantly limits the size of the areas that can be studied. The reconstruction of structures becomes an arduous task when the period under investigation is not covered, or only covered in part, by archival material. This issue assumes particular significance in the context of the study of formerly rural areas over extended periods.

References:

Psenner A, Kodydek K (2017). Researching the morphology of the city's internal micro structure: UPM Urban Parterre Modelling. 10.4995/ISUF2017.2017.5115.

Psenner A (2023) Stadtparterre. Erdgeschoss, Straße, Hof und deren Übergänge. Jovis, Berlin

Concept Figure UPMsmart

1.3 UPMsmart

UPMsmart eschews the original approach of documenting each building individually and modelling it 3D—both historically and in its current state—using CAD software. Instead UPMsmart operates with a catalogue of pre-modelled building types (UPMsmart Objects resp. UPMsmOb). The production of these items is founded upon reconstructions derived from historical cartographic materials, including maps and images (illustrations and photographs), as well as architectural blueprints for the different building types. UPMsmOb is constituted by a solid model of the building, a detailed façade model and a modelled ground-floor space defined by its intended use. Depending on the requirements of the project, a representative and suitable UPMsmOb is selected for the relevant time period based on expert knowledge and positioned within the CAD-model. In instances where a contemporary building is not present in a historical state, a suitable UPMsmOb is selected on the basis of the building footprint, as delineated on a historical map. Consequently, the 3D city model of UPMsmart does not reflect the exactness of UPM in relation to the actual built object; nevertheless, relevant building parameters and qualities can be abstractly replicated in UPMsmart in order to make qualitative statements about the respective study area in accordance with the original UPM method. The primary benefit of the modified UPMsmart method is that it significantly reduces the time required for the workflow, thereby allowing for the theoretical expansion of the study areas to a neighbourhood level. Furthermore, it facilitates the analysis of periods or areas where the extensive data set required for a UPM is not available.

1.4 Morphological Background

A key aspect of both the original UPM and the adapted UPMsmart methodology the comparison of historical and contemporary conditions using morphological approaches, thereby facilitating the drawing of conclusions about spatial developments or genesis. In the context of the Vienna case study and the preliminary investigation of four selected linear settlements, the following time periods were identified and selected for analysis:

1820's is based on the Franzsizeischen Katasters (1817-29)

1910's is based on the Generalstadtplans 1912

2020s is based on the contemporary situation

UPMsmart Framework

1820s
1910s
2020s

3 Sequences

Current
Situation

2.1 Framework UPMsmart

As outlined above, UPMsmart employs a methodology that involves the comparison of a current state with two historical states and the subsequent analysis of these states in terms of their spatial distribution. This approach is predicated on a CAD-based 3D city model that depicts the three time periods and incorporates microstructural qualities and spatial information. In the UPMsmart methodology, selected sequences are analysed to draw conclusions about larger areas of study, at the level of the urban tissues or on neighbourhood level. The following three components are prerequisites for this:

- typological Catalogue
- data input with spatial informations
- set of rules for reconstruction

In addition to analysing and evaluating information embedded in the CAD model, UPMsmart is designed to function as a City Information Model (CIM).

Mapping historical uses (1910s)

Typological classification

Mapping current uses (2020s)

2.2 Framework UPMsmart

The generation of a UPMsmart CAD model necessitates the utilisation of three additional key datasets, in addition to the vectorised historical maps produced as deliverable D 3.2 under the EMC2 research project.

- The study has been conducted using historical usage data collated from various sources, including historical address books Adolph Lehmann's Allgemeiner Wohnungs-Anzeiger (General Housing Index) from 1912 is a seminal publication in the field. The following categories are given consideration: The following sectors are represented: manufacturing industry, commercial, service, gastronomy, residential, vacancy/storage, garage/stable, and other.

- The mapping of current usages is achieved through the implementation of on-site inspections. The following categories are given consideration: manufacturing industry, commercial, service, gastronomy, residential, vacancy/storage, garage/stable, and other.

- The survey covers a typological classification of the buildings within the area under investigation. For further reference, please see: Typological Catalogue. In accordance with the typological classification, three representative sequences have been selected for in-depth modelling and analysis.

References

Adolph Lehmann's allgemeiner Wohnungs-Anzeiger : nebst Handels- u. Gewerbe-Adressbuch für d. k.k. Reichshaupt- u. Residenzstadt Wien u. Umgebung. Wien : Österreichische Anzeigen-Gesellschaft, 1. Jahrgang (1859)-63. Jahrgang (1921/22), 1859-1922 : (1912). Wienbibliothek im Rathaus, <https://resolver.obvsg.at/urn:nbn:at:AT-WBR-486378> / Public Domain Mark 1.0

2.3 Framework UPMsmart Typological Catalogue

The buildings within the designated study area are divided into four distinct time periods:

- first half of the 19th century and earlier
- second half of the 19th century
- 20th century
- 21st century

Due to the distinctive characteristics of the typical historical farmstead types, they are highlighted separately and do replace the first chronological period. The catalogue encompasses a selection of historical, region-specific building types, with a particular focus on those from the 19th century. In addition to these, it also features a more extensive array of building types from classical modernism and the present day. In conjunction with a typological classification of building footprints, the catalogue also comprises a selection of representative facades that are compatible with the building types, featuring corresponding architectural styles. The typological classification, the building form and the corresponding facade form the basis for the building, resp. UPMsmOb., which is imported into the CAD model. This UPMsmOb. is then enhanced with spatial information, both historical and contemporary (Ref. 2.6. CIM), thereby becoming a kind of abstracted digital building avatar.

2.4 UPMsmart Set of Rules

The establishment of a codified set of modelling rules and standards is imperative for the conduct of modelling and the reconstruction of historical states. The historical models are to be regarded as abstract representations, which are likely to diverge from the actual situation. However, the utilisation of expert knowledge, built upon available historic material (documents, images, plans, etc.) and the incorporation of historical map materials that facilitate the discernment of building footprints, probable building types, resp. UPMsmOb., enables an abstract historical reconstruction.

- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

2.5. UPMsmart Evaluations

The UPMsmart model provides opportunities for evaluations and corresponding visualisations based on exportable floor plans and sections. At present, three analyses or evaluations for this UPMsmart analysis are addressed in section 5. The schematic approach employed at the building level necessitates the designation of a specific area in which to locate the identifies usage during the analysis - the morphologically decoded building logic yields a fixed depth of 4 metres for this purpose; no individual square-based evaluations are carried out. The building-related considerations of permeability (of the ground floor façade) and usage are counted in numerical terms. The analysis of the proportion of street space available to pedestrians is conducted on a square-metre basis and as a percentage.

The following three analysis parameters are applied to all three time periods and subsequently compared – Ref.

- 1) Permeability: the number of access points within the sequences.
- 2) Uses, frequencies and changes: Which and how many usage types are found? Manufacturing Industry, Commercial, Service, Gastronomy, Residential, Vacancy/Storage, Garage/Stable, Other
- 3) Usable space for pedestrians within the streetscape

Usage 1912

- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

Building type

- Hist. farmstead types
- Hist. farmstead types adapt.
- City 2nd half 19th cent.
- City 20th cent.
- City 21st cent.

Previous parcelling

- Yes
- No

Corresponding Address

- Individual

Usage 2024

- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

2.6. City Information Modeling (CIM)

UPMsmart integrates selected OGD datasets from the City of Vienna – predominantly GIS datasets – with custom-built architectural CAD building models. These building models are underpinned by the principles of Building Information Modelling (BIM) and are enriched with pertinent building information for various classifications and architectural components. The integration of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Building Information Modelling (BIM) represents a central approach within the domain of City Information Modelling (CIM). UPMsmart aligns itself accordingly within this CIM framework.

Used data sets from the City of Vienna (OGD):

For modeling process

Mehrweckkarte (MZK) Vektordaten, Link: <https://www.wien.gv.at/stadtplanung/mehrweckkarte-daten-beziehen>

Generalisiertes Dachmodell (LOD2.1), Link: <https://www.wien.gv.at/stadtplanung/generalisiertes-dachmodell>

Geländemodell (DGM), Link: <https://www.wien.gv.at/stadtplanung/digitales-gelaendemodell>

For historical analysis and evaluation, these maps have been previously vectorised within this research project as party of deliverable D 3.2 and can be accessed here:

Franziseischer Kataster (1829), Link: <https://www.wien.gv.at/kultur/kulturgut-plaene-franziseisch>

Generalstadtplan (1912), Link: <https://www.wien.gv.at/kultur/kulturgut-plaene-generalstadtplan>

UPMsmart Modelling Protocol

2020s

UPMsmart Modelling Protocol

The CAD modelling in UPMsmart is partly based on the principle of reverse engineering. First, the current situation of the case study is modelled. This state is also the starting point for the first historical period (the 1910s), with buildings historically associated with this period being copied and adapted. Subsequently, a check is carried out to see whether these adopted and now adapted buildings can be transferred to the second historical period (1820s), followed by further adaptation. Afterwards, the 1820s period is then finalised. Buildings that can be referenced from the 1820s period to the 1910s situation are transferred to the 1910s period. Buildings constructed between the 1820s and 1910s are added to complete the situation around 1910, and the 1910s situation is finalised in the final step.

Three-dimensional CAD modelling of the time period: 2020s

Step 1^{2020s} Import of: Mehrzweckkarte (MZK), Generalisiertes Dachmodell (LOD2.1) and Geländemodell (DGM) — OGD's — into CAD Software

Step 2^{2020s} Re-modelling of the facade level based on photographs and on-site analysis, carried out in an abstract manner using expert knowledge. For historic façades dating from around 1900 or earlier, consideration is given to certain typical dimensions, for example in window openings. The respective façade models for each building are saved as grouped objects independently of the number of storeys and catalogued in a locally stored digital library (Ref. Typological Catalogue). As the inventory of abstract facades and edifices continues to expand within the Catalogue, the work process is progressively diminishing due to the increased utilisation of pre-modelled facade types.

Step 3^{2020s} Modelling of a schematic ground floor room unit with a fixed depth of 4 metres. Allocation of ground floor use based on site visits, according to the following categories: Manufacturing; Retail; Services; Gastronomy; Residential; Subjective vacancy; Storage; Garage, stable; Other; Not assessable

Step 4^{2020s} Subdivision of the Geländemodell (DGM) in the street area into green spaces, pavements and roadways in accordance with the MZK. The road area is lowered by 10cm, whilst the green spaces in the street area are raised by 5cm.

Step 5^{2020s} An abstract reconstruction of the tree stock based on the City of Vienna's tree register, which is accessible via a web browser and contains information on tree height and crown width.

Step 6^{2020s} Integration of parking lots in public spaces based on site visits

2020s

1910s

UPMsmart Modelling Protocol

First part of the Three-dimensional CAD modelling of the time period: 1910s

Step 1^{1910s} Those buildings from the current situation that can also be referenced to the first historical period are initially incorporated into this first historical model. Subsequently, the windows in the respective facades – which were generally replaced in the second half of the 20th cent. or in the 21st cent. – are adjusted. These windows are modelled as historical windows.

Three-dimensional CAD modelling of the time period: 1820s

Step 1^{1820s} The modified buildings from the 1910s are checked to see whether they can also be incorporated into the 1820s time period. Suitable buildings are then incorporated and transferred to the second historical state (1820s), where they are adapted again. In this process, window sizes, for example, are adjusted. The remaining buildings, which no longer existed in 2020, are selected from the UPMsmart catalogue primarily with the aid of an analysis of historical map data (Franzischeischer Kataster 1817–1829) and placed in the model. Equally relevant to this process are expert knowledge, typomorphological analysis and an understanding of common, recurring floor plans within the respective buildings.

Step 2^{1820s} Modelling of the schematic ground-floor room unit in the historic buildings. For this period, the hybrid use of 'farming and living' was invented, reflecting the agricultural character of the linear settlements.

Step 3^{1820s} The Geländmodell from the 2020s has been adopted — even though historically there may well have been different elevations. Elevation differences within the street network were disregarded and not modelled due to a lack of detail in the map data from the 1820s.

Step 4^{1820s} Trees were neglected and not modelled due to a lack of detail in the maps from the 1820s.

Step 5^{1820s} Any adjustments at street level were omitted and not modelled due to a lack of detail in the map data from the 1820s.

1820s

1910s

UPMsmart Modelling Protocol

Finalisation of the Three-dimensional CAD modelling of the time period: 1910s

Step 2^{1910s} Buildings and facades from the 1820s, some of which are also found in the 1910s building footprint, are transferred to the 1910s model and adjusted where necessary. The remaining buildings are selected primarily by analysing a historical map base from the UPMsmart catalogue and placed in the model. Equally relevant to this process are expert knowledge, typomorphological analysis and an understanding of common, recurring floor plans within the respective buildings.

Step 3^{1910s} Modelling of the schematic ground floor room unit in the newly added historic buildings. Selection of appropriate ground floor uses based on the mapping of historical uses.

Step 4^{1910s} Adoption of the Geländemodell from the 2020s — even though historically there may have been different levels. Where visible in historical map material, reproduction of edges in the street environment, again with a 10 cm drop in elevation.

Step 5^{1910s} Where visible on historical maps, the placement of a symbolic tree with fixed dimensions.

Step 6^{1910s} Any modifications at street level, such as the reproduction of tram tracks or similar features

UPMsmart Components

2020s

1910s

1820s

UPMsmart Components

4.1 Buildings

The building volumes in the current state are derived from the Generalisiertes Dachmodell (LOD 2.1). Where possible, parts of this building model are also carried over into historical states. The buildings in the two historical states are reconstructed on the basis of historical map data. Building heights are based either on directly adjacent buildings of a comparable type, where available, or, if no height reference is available, they are derived from typical, referenceable buildings from the UPMsmart catalogue.

Adoption of the roof shape from OGD

2020s

Adjustment to the height
of main building
or 2.50m or 3.50m

ca.35°

1910s

ca.35°

Adjustment to the height
of main building
or 2.50m or 3.50m

1820s

UPMsmart Components

4.2 Roofs

The roof shapes of the current state result from the Generalisiertes Dachmodell (LOD2.1). This basis also provides insights into typical historical roof shapes. When reconstructing building types no longer extant, such as houses from the Gründerzeit era or even older farmstead types, roof angles of 30° or 35° are selected.

The side cross-wings extending into the plots do not have specific angles, but are adapted to the eaves and ridge lines of the street-facing wing. If the cross-wing extending into the plot is staggered in the building footprint – often the case with historic courtyard-style buildings due to attached outbuildings – these are slightly stepped down in height. In the absence of a height reference from the current state, detached buildings in the vicinity of the main building are to be drawn with an eaves height of either 2.50 m or 3.50 m (depending on building heights within the plot) or, where appropriate, aligned with surrounding existing roof heights based on expert knowledge. The greater degree of uncertainty in the reconstruction of these subordinate buildings is tolerated; however, modelling them as schematic volumes is relevant for understanding within the model.

2020s

original windows remaining

Adjusting windows to original state

Adjusting windows to original state

1910s

Adapting gate

Adapting window sizes in second hist. state

1820s

UPMsmart Components

4.3 Openings

Windows

The modelling of windows in the UPMsmart modell in the contemporary time period is based on on-site inspections, photographs as well as on a expert knowledge. As previously expounded in Section 3, a replacement with more modern windows has been undertaken in most historic farmstead types that are extant today. Historic windows have undergone a marked decline in number. Accordingly, these windows were incorporated into the model and recreated while maintaining the original, characteristic six-pane layout, using the standard dimensions of the Gründerzeit, such as ca.120 x 180 cm. In certain extant farmstead types, which were not built or adapted during the Gründerzeit, smaller window dimensions, such as approximately 100x140 cm, can still be found.

Doors and Gates

The modelling of doors and gates in the UPMsmart modell in the contemporary time period is based on expert knowledge, on-site inspections and photographs. In the context of historic farmstead types, the majority of buildings were accessed via the courtyard side, with a gate or passageway situated in the street. The gates are measured at a width and height of 2–3 m. Moreover, in the absence of specific information during the 1820s and 1910s, a curved archway was modelled in preference to a straight horizontal beam.

Stucco

Stucco work is abstractly recreated on historical facades as well as frames are added around windows and doors.

1820s

1820s

1820s

UPMsmart Components

4.4 Gates, Fences

Gates and fences situated alongside farmstead buildings are primarily characteristic in historical periods. Although these structures are now found only sporadically, historically they were frequently characterised by farmstead types with their gables oriented towards the main street. Nevertheless, it is notable that this open area alongside the building at the front of the plot was frequently enclosed by a wall and a gateway. Since no actual data is available for the historical periods (walls are not displayed in historical maps), this principle was adopted for the historical periods. The width of the gates was assumed to be 2–3m.

In instances where open areas adjacent to the building exceeded 6m, it was hypothesised that no wall existed in these locations; therefore, a fence was modelled.

2020s

1910s

1820s

UPMsmart Components

4.5 Streets

In its present state, the model includes the pavement level, the road level, green spaces, parking lots and tree plantings. The initial point of departure is the Geländemodell (DGM) and the Mehrzweckkarte (MZK) of the City of Vienna (OGD). The Geländemodell is a surface model that does not, for example, account for differences in elevation between the pavement and the road level. Based on the Mehrzweckkarte, pavement edges and green spaces are identified and the surface is divided into three layers. The road level is lowered by 10cm, while the green spaces are elevated by 5cm. Parking lots are also integrated into the road level.

The 1910s map base, the Generalstadtplan 1912, depicts certain edges or, for example, tram tracks. In a similar manner, certain elevation accents were integrated into the scheme on the basis of expert knowledge. The Geländemodell (DGM) from the 2020s was once again utilised as the basis for this modelling state.

However, due to the paucity of data available for the 1820s time period, the current Geländemodell (DGM) was utilised again.

2020s

1910s

UPMsmart Components

4.6 Trees

The trees are modelled using the City of Vienna's tree register, which is available on the website <https://www.wien.gv.at/umweltgut/public/grafik.aspx?ThemePage=11>. This includes, for instance, crown width and height, which are specified, for example, as ,6–8 m'. In this case, the respective average value is calculated and used to remodel the tree in the CAD model.

Symbolic trees are marked on the base maps dating from around 1910. Accordingly, a schematic tree with fixed dimensions has been used: the crown width is 7m and the tree height is 10m. Due to a lack of source data, no tree plantings have been depicted in the CAD model for the 1820s.

UPMsmart Components

4.7 Usages

To illustrate the usage of the ground floor, a schematic room unit with a fixed depth of 4m is integrated into the building. As historical uses in particular cannot be assigned to a specific location within the floorplan, the approach adopted was to represent all uses as columns in the schematic ground-floor space. Consequently, in instances where a single address is utilised for multiple purposes, two, three or more bars are displayed within the spatial unit.

The present usage of the site is based on the results of site visits. In order to ascertain the usage of the term around 1910, the historian and architect Friedrich Hauer was assigned the task of evaluating address books in order to identify the relevant uses in selected linear settlements and their respective surrounding contexts. In the context of the 1820s, the absence of registers or analogous records precludes the possibility of a comparable investigation. During this period, the hybrid use of 'Farming+Living' was identified for all buildings that were not marked with special uses (like churches or inns) in historical maps, reflecting the rural character of the village structures. In instances where no specific alternative use could be identified through research in the 1910 address books, this hybrid use, 'Farming+Living', was also applied to farmstead buildings around 1910.

UPMsmart on four selected linear settlements

Linear settlement 1

Sequenz 1

Sequenz 2

1820s

1910s

2020s

Evaluation Linear settlement 1

Name Linear Settlement: Untersievering

District: 19th, Döbling

Relation in Network (WP3): On

Built transformation (WP3): Medium Transformation

Site Plan WP3.2, buildings marked in red identify those objects that can be referenced to typical historic farmsteads

1820s

1910s

2020s

Sequenz 3

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- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

1820s

S1

S2

S3

1910s

S1

S2

S3

2020s

S1

Evaluation Linear settlement 1

	1820s				1910s				2020s			
	S1	S2	S3	Total	S1	S2	S3	Total	S1	S2	S3	Total
Number of Buildings	2	7	4	13	4	7	7	18	6	7	7	20
Building-integrated access	0	6	4	10	1	7	4	12	2	7	4	13
Detached gate, fence	2	1	0	3	3	0	3	6	4	0	3	7
Usages												
Living +Farming	2	7	4	13	3	3	4	10	0	0	0	0
Manufacturing Industry	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0
Commercial	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Service	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Gastronomy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	3
Residential	0	0	0	0	1	4	3	8	4	6	5	15
Vacancy / Storage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Garage / Stable	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	5
Other	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	0	2
Hybrid usage												
Double	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	1	0	1
Triple	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Fourfold	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pedestrian Space	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	37%	33%	36%	35%

S2

S3

- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

Linear settlement 2

1820s

1910s

2020s

Sequenz 1

Sequenz 2

Evaluation Linear settlement 2

Name Linear Settlement: Großjedlersdorf

District: 21st, Floridsdorf

Relation in Network (WP3): Parallel

Built transformation (WP3): Low transformation

Site Plan WP3.2, buildings marked in red identify those objects that can be referenced to typical historic farmsteads

1820s

1910s

2020s

Sequenz 3

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- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

1820s

S1

S2

S3

1910s

2020s

Evaluation Linear settlement 2

S1

S2

S3

	1820s				1910s				2020s			
	S1	S2	S3	Total	S1	S2	S3	Total	S1	S2	S3	Total
Number of Buildings	9	7	7	23	9	7	7	23	6	7	6	19
Building-integrated access	2	6	4	12	9	7	7	23	6	7	6	19
Detached gate, fence	7	1	3	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Usages												
Living +Farming	9	7	7	23	6	7	5	18	0	0	0	0
Manufacturing Industry	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Commercial	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Service	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Gastronomy	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	2	2
Residential	0	0	0	0	3	0	2	5	6	7	4	17
Vacancy / Storage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Garage / Stable	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Other	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
Hybrid usage												
Double	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
Triple	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0
Fourfold	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pedestrian Space	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	28%	51%	39%	39%

- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

Linear settlement 3

1820s

1910s

2020s

Sequenz 1

Sequenz 2

Evaluation Linear settlement 3

Name Linear Settlement: Leopoldau
 District: 21st, Floridsdorf
 Relation in Network (WP3): Perpendicular
 Built transformation (WP3): Low transformation

Site Plan WP3.2, buildings marked in red identify those objects that can be referenced to typical historic farmsteads

1820s

1910s

2020s

- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

1820s

S1

S2

S3

1910s

2020s

S1

S2

S3

Evaluation Linear settlement 3

	1820s				1910s				2020s			
	S1	S2	S3	Total	S1	S2	S3	Total	S1	S2	S3	Total
Number of Buildings	7	8	8	23	7	8	8	23	7	8	8	23
Building-integrated access	3	6	1	10	7	8	6	21	7	8	8	23
Detached gate, fence	3	2	7	12	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	0
Usages												
Living +Farming	7	8	8	23	5	3	8	16	0	0	0	0
Manufacturing Industry	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	3	0	0	0	0
Commercial	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	3	0	1	0	1
Service	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3
Gastronomy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2
Residential	0	0	0	0	2	5	0	7	6	4	8	18
Vacancy / Storage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	3
Garage / Stable	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0
Hybrid usage												
Double	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3	0	1	0	1
Triple	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	0	1	0	1
Fourfold	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pedestrian Space	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	39%	50%	74%	54%

- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

Linear settlement 4

Sequenz 1

Sequenz 2

1820s

1910s

2020s

Evaluation Linear settlement 4

Name Linear Settlement: Simmering
District: 11th, Simmering
Relation in Network (WP3): Perpendicular
Built transformation (WP3): Medium Transformation

Site Plan WP3.2, buildings marked in red identify those objects that can be referenced to typical historic farmsteads

1820s

1910s

2020s

Sequenz 3

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- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

1820s

S1

S2

S3

1910s

S1

S2

S3

2020s

S1

S2

S3

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Evaluation Linear settlement 4

	1820s				1910s				2020s			
	S1	S2	S3	Total	S1	S2	S3	Total	S1	S2	S3	Total
Number of Buildings	4	7	4	15	6	7	3	16	5	7	3	15
Building-integrated access	2	1	1	4	5	3	3	11	5	6	3	14
Detached gate, fence	2	6	3	11	1	4	0	5	0	1	0	1
Usages												
Living +Farming	4	7	3	14	1	5	2	8	0	0	0	0
Manufacturing Industry	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0
Commercial	0	0	0	0	3	2	1	6	0	0	0	0
Service	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	2	0	5
Gastronomy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Residential	0	0	0	0	4	2	1	7	3	5	2	10
Vacancy / Storage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	3
Garage / Stable	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Hybrid usage												
Double	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	4	1	1	0	2
Triple	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0
Fourfold	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pedestrian Space	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	33%	41%	35%	36%

- Manufacturing Industry
- Commercial
- Service
- Gastronomy
- Residential
- Vacancy, Storage
- Garage, Stable
- Other
- Residential + Farming

Observations

The production of CAD models of four different settlements for three periods respectively allows for the analysis of the settlements over time, as well as a comparison of the settlements at each time frame and their entire evolution. Generally, in the models, we can observe different areas, most prominently: the buildings, the uses and the public space.

In all four settlements, a trend towards increased building density can be observed, particularly an increase in built-up area along the boundary with public spaces. While small intervals between the row of houses along the eaves were always closed off by gates (see 4.4), the larger gaps gradually disappeared, resulting in a more continuous street frontage and therefore also a more enclosed street space. Building heights are also getting taller across all settlements, as shown by the prototypical modelling, although the effect is more pronounced in newer developments than in existing buildings, which have generally only been extended by one storey. Here, a distinction can be made both between different settlements and between the different sections of the same settlement; whilst some areas stand out early on as having higher buildings, there are areas that remain characterised by single-storey buildings until today. However, no clear conclusions can be drawn here regarding a connection with the location of the section (at the ends or in the middle of the settlement).

Uses in the ground-floor zone are evolving, in line with the modelling logic, from an initial uniform residential + farming usage in the 1820s to a greater diversification of uses. Whilst in the 1910s, alongside the continuation of farming + residential uses, purely residential use became dominant, some settlements are also characterised by manufacturing and commercial uses. In contrast, in the 2020s the settlements are even more strongly characterised by residential use, but gastronomy, service and vacancy, storage uses can also be observed in the ground floor zone - with the exception of one settlement (No.2), which is notable for being exclusively residential.

The model does not provide a clearly observable picture of how the distribution of public space has evolved, due to the lack of available data for earlier periods. A comparison of today's distribution of public space between the settlements however reveals, in particular, that the expansion of the street space into a so-called Anger has a positive effect both on the amount of space available to pedestrians and on the proportion of green space. As regards the trees, a precise analysis is also difficult due to a lack of baseline data; however, if the assumption is made that the trees shown on the plans from the 1910s while not necessarily reflecting the exact number of trees present, but accurately indicating their general presence, it is only in one settlement (No.4) where trees can be observed in public spaces in the 2020s where none existed in the previous time frame.

Methodological Discussion

As outlined, the theoretical intention of UPMsmart is to operate with a catalogue of pre-modelled, abstract building models and facades in order to generate 3D CAD-based city models in both their present and historical states. The individual building models represent certain building types in a highly simplified form; the composition of these models is explained in section 4. The selection of comparable building types or UPMsmOb is made on the basis of expert knowledge, with the addition of historical map material in the case of historical modelling. These are then positioned within the model from the catalogue.

The UPMsmart city models are not designed to provide an exact representation of actual situations or historical reconstructions. In accordance with the relevant principles and rules within UPMsmart modelling, situations are simplified and, in the historical representation of the models, are to be understood as assumptions. This approach consequently involves a higher degree of imprecision and deviation from contemporary and historical situations, which are addressed with greater precision in the original UPM methodology.

This analysis of linear settlements represents the initial UPMsmart analysis. Consequently, this analysis also served to collect and generate relevant building types and façades for the expanding catalogue. In addition to the uncertainties regarding architectural accuracy and the historical reconstruction of past situations, one of the greatest deficiencies of this approach – especially when compared to the original methodology – is the representation of the schematic ground-floor layout. Furthermore, mapping based on historical address books does not allow for the exact localisation of spaces within the floor plan to be determined. Consequently, a representation using schematic usage bars was used for multiple uses. This status quo regarding the ground floor and its uses is to be improved in the future. Furthermore, it is not possible to reconstruct the spatial characteristics at street level satisfactorily due to a lack of relevant information.

In contrast, the value of this approach is apparent in its ability to enable the swift and effective creation of computer-aided design (CAD)-based city models, even in circumstances where data regarding the historical situation is scarce. This capacity to extract valuable insights into qualitative aspects and illustrate assumptions concerning urban development processes is a significant benefit. The systematic progression from UPM to UPMsmart facilitates the analysis of larger study areas using artificial intelligence (AI), based on a catalogue of building types and façades. It can be argued that this could also render the current approach of working with representativesquences obsolete.

Conclusio

The UPMsmart analysis produced CAD-based CIM models that address the urban development, as well as the spatial qualities and characteristics, of selected linear settlements in Vienna. A key asset of both UPM and UPMsmart is their capacity to illustrate all constituent structural and architectural features within a single model or via a 3D sectional perspective along a street frontage. The presentation of this sectional perspective in historical and contemporary states also facilitates analysis of the transformation of street space character and corresponding uses.

The examination of two historical periods within the UPMsmart study enables the identification of potential architectural transformations in the extant village structures. On the one hand, traditional farmstead types underwent continuous evolution, whilst on the other, the 1910s period witnessed the emergence of the first three-storey residential buildings from the Gründerzeit period. At this stage, a discernible transformation in the street profile became evident in certain instances. Subsequently, the implementation of raised and lowered ground floors (Souterrain and Hochparterre) resulted in the creation of distinct spatial levels in relation to the street space. The general evolution of street profiles gives rise to new relationships regarding lighting and shading, as evidenced by recent studies in the field.

The persistence of the characteristic narrow, elongated plots and the associated farm types result in a comparatively high degree of continuity within the base zone, featuring numerous access points and openings. It is evident that due to an absence of data sources, no PoI mapping was conducted for the 1820s. The prevailing focus on agriculture and subsistence living in the period preceding the emancipation of the farmers as serfs in the mid-19th century is indicative of an agricultural orientation. Consequently, as a result of social developments and increasing urbanisation, alternative uses and specialisations can increasingly be identified for the 1910s. With regard to the present period of the 2020s, dominating residential uses can be documented in three out of four linear settlements (No.1, No.2, No.3).

Three of the four villages examined exhibit a slightly higher proportion of space designated exclusively for pedestrians — slightly over a third — than in a typical residential street from the Gründerzeit period or certain other street types in Vienna. However, it is evident that prior to the implementation of the Road Traffic Regulations (RTR) in 1938, the carriageway itself was predominantly intended for pedestrian use (Psenner, 2023). The area referred to as the ‚Anger‘, which is characterised by a particular type of linear settlement (No.3), was historically used for agricultural and community activities and currently functions as a green space that offers some recreational amenities. This additional open space results in an increase in the proportion of pedestrian space in the village of Leopoldau to over 50% in this current sequence. It is evident that, while historical periods have demonstrated that street space was entirely utilised by pedestrians, height differentiations in the surface level had already been integrated into the street cross-section.

The initial scope of the deliverable – ‘Numeric 3D models of main streets in their present state’ – was expanded in the course of this study by generating 3D models not only of current situations but also of historical situations, thereby establishing a stronger link to WP3 and enabling the traceability of the evolution of the settlements on different scales and using different analytical approaches. The present study was thus grounded in the following questions: How have historically built structures along historic main streets changed morphologically? What spatial qualities and usage patterns can be found in specific peri-urban patterns, such as in the case of linear settlement structures? Two key takeaways emerge in relation to the EMC2 concept:

1) Historical linear settlements are defined by ongoing adaptations and transformations in settlement patterns, whilst retaining the basic layout as a permanent or persistent feature.

The historically evolved character of these settlements, in conjunction with the establishment of designated protection zones, renders them less susceptible to change in comparison with other suburban patterns. However, this detailed study over a relevant period also reveals the adaptability of these historic village structures and their spatial qualities. Even in linear settlements characterised by a high proportion of historic buildings, the detailed examination unveils the various transformations across different eras – as evidenced by the analysis of the sequences of the four villages studied. Furthermore, the respective village structures underwent independent transformations, regardless of their function or changes of function within the network (as part of the historic or today's main street mesh/foreground network).

The original farmstead building typologies are characterised by narrow plots and small-scale, single storey structures, in addition to a direct relationship to street level, adaptations were comparably minor and carried out by means of building expansions or an additional storey. The introduction of new building types in the late 19th or 20th century resulted in alterations to the scale of the buildings, characterised by an increase in building size, this applies to both height and footprint, as well as the introduction of multi-unit buildings. As is often the case, these later typologies are associated with a raised ground floor situation, which in turn creates different reference levels in relation to street level.

The transformations undergone by these linear settlement structures serve to illustrate the adaptability of street space and at the building level response to evolving requirements. The EMC2 model for the 15 Minute City, which is designed for implementation within existing peri-urban contexts that are naturally characterised by a variety of existing typologies and qualities, can draw on these findings to assess possibilities for the adaptation of existing structures, but also to realise the potential for densification with adequate building typologies.

2) Adaptable ground-floor uses within historic linear settlements

The analysis of the linear settlement structures reveals that, within small-scale spatial units, diverse categories of use (ranging from dominant productive uses centred around 1910 to, for example, gastronomy or services in the 2020s) can emerge over time, whereas this is not the case for larger spaces such as typical retail units (i.e. supermarkets). Smaller units

Link to EMC2

therefore demonstrate greater resilience in the face of change; this can be a key component in the effective and sustainable implementation of a 15-minute city. The analysis also reveals a general shift in land use patterns over time. The direction of this shift is not uniform across all village structures and is directly linked to the immediate surrounding context (e.g. a stronger focus on gastronomy in areas relevant to tourism).

As highlighted in point 1, a notable characteristic of the original farmstead types is the direct connection between the ground floor and street level. This offers the potential for creating small-scale, flexible-use units that can be opened up to the street space without the need for major modifications. In principle, the integration of amenities and infrastructure tailored to the requirements of 15-minute cities could be a viable component of this development.

D 5.3a Numeric 3D-models of main streets in their present situation:

Analysis of historical linear settlements and their development applying the UPM Smart methodology

Authors:

Angelika Psenner

Daniel Loeschenbrand

Susanne Tobisch

TU Wien

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